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EXPERIENCE

TÉLÉCOM PARIS (LTCI) | PHD

Defended on the 09/09/2025 | Palaiseau, France

- Study of longitudinal Power Profile Estimation (PPE) techniques in core optical telecommunication links
- Study of Variational AutoEncoder-based FIR equaliser for Probabilistic Constellation Shaping transmission

| PUBLICATIONS

- *louis tomczyk et. al.*, "Relaxing dispersion pre-distorsion constraints of receiver-based power profile estimators", OECC 2023
- *louis tomczyk et. al.*, "Blind State of Polarisation Monitoring Using Variational AutoEncoders-inspired Adaptive Filter", ECOC 2024
- *louis tomczyk et. al.*, "Blind Polarisation Demultiplexing and Carrier Recovery Using FIR-based Variational AutoEncoder Equaliser for Probabilistic Constellation Shaping in Optical Fibre Communications", JLT 2025

| TEACHINGS

- Fourier optics, holography and fibre physics (tutorials and practical work): 80 hours
- Semiconductor physics (tutorial): 15 hours

BKTEL PHOTONICS | PRODUCT ENGINEER

09/2020 - 08/2021 | Lannion, France

- Development (design, fabrication, testing - DFT) of a 20 [W], 1060 [nm] PM CW laser with high stability (RMS= 0.1%) and a 100 [W], 1040 [nm] laser.
- Development (DFT) and characterisation of EDFA (flatness, NF).
- Development (design, implementation, testing) of tools for production, automation and security of measurements using Python.

PROJECTS

LASER DIODE NOISES SIMULATION | MATLAB®

ENSSAT | 2021

- Numerical simulation of phase and RIN noise of laser diodes in CW regime, from the coupled equations of evolution of intensity, photon number and phase.
- Yielding relationship between Henry factor α and FN noise levels.

LASER NOISE REDUCTION BEYOND THE QUANTUM LIMIT

ENSSAT | 2021

- Study of laser noise reduction techniques beyond the shot noise (quantum limit) using squeezed states.
- Setup using acousto-optic modulator, SHG and OPO.

MACHINE LEARNING PROJECTS | PYTHON

Xidian University | 2021

- Imprecision and uncertainty in evidential clustering based on the Dempster-Shafer theory. Suggestion of formalism and standardisation of metrics to quantify a global performance of a soft-partitioning algorithm.

SKILLS

PROGRAMMING

Python (numpy, sci-kit learn, pandas) • MATLAB • L^AT_EX

LANGUAGES

English (fluent), Russian (A1), French (native),

EDUCATION

TÉLÉCOM PARIS

PHD IN OPTICAL

TELECOMMUNICATIONS

04/2022 - 09/2025 | Palaiseau, France

XIDIAN UNIVERSITY

ACADEMIC SEMESTER IN AI

09/2021 - 02/2022 | Xi'an, China

ENSSAT

ENGINEERING DEGREE IN Photonics

2017/2021 | Lannion, France

CERTIFICATIONS

COURSERA MOOC

NON LINEAR OPTICS

Polytechnic School of Paris - M. JOFFRE

FUN MOOC

INTRODUCTION TO QUANTUM PHYSICS

Polytechnic School of Paris - D.

BOSCHETTO

OC MOOC

MACHINE LEARNING

CentraleSupélec - C.A. AZENCOTT

HOBBIES

Solo travelling across Eurasia

Astrophysics

REFERENCES

Élie AWWAD, Associate

Professor at Télécom Paris

✉ elie.awwad@telecom-paris.fr

Stéphane TREBAOL, Associate

Professor at ENSSAT- FOTON

✉ trebaol@enssat.fr